

Awareness and Perception of Librarians towards Implementation of Blockchain for Library Service Delivery in Federal University Libraries, Northern Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the awareness, perception, and challenges associated with the implementation of blockchain technology for library service delivery in Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria. The research was guided by two research questions and three corresponding null hypotheses. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, with a population of seventy-two librarians working in the E-library divisions of nine federal university libraries. Data were collected using a validated questionnaire with a reliability coefficient of 0.83 and analyzed using mean, standard deviation, chi-square, and one-sample t-test at a 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that librarians demonstrated a low overall level of awareness of blockchain technology (Cluster Mean = 2.23 ± 0.60), although they showed basic understanding of its concepts and potential benefits for enhancing digital security, transparency, and resource management. However, librarians exhibited a high level of perception (Cluster Mean = 3.44 ± 1.17), indicating strong optimism regarding blockchain's relevance and transformative potential in improving library operations, record integrity, and service efficiency. The study also identified significant challenges hindering blockchain implementation (Cluster Mean = 3.73 ± 1.18), including high costs, inadequate infrastructure, limited technical expertise, integration difficulties, policy and legal uncertainties, and institutional resistance. Hypotheses testing showed significant differences in librarians' awareness ($\chi^2 = 87.68$, $p < 0.05$) and perception ($\chi^2 = 9.697$, $p < 0.05$) across institutions, while challenges associated with blockchain implementation were found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The study concludes that despite librarians' positive perception of blockchain technology, its adoption in Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria is constrained by structural, technical, and institutional barriers. The study recommends professional training, infrastructure development, policy formulation, and strategic planning to enhance blockchain adoption in academic library services.

Keyword: Blockchain, awareness, perception, service delivery & Federal university libraries.

Introduction

The rapid advancement of emerging technologies continues to reshape information management and service delivery across various sectors, including libraries. Among these innovations, blockchain technology has attracted increasing scholarly and professional attention due to its decentralized structure, transparency, and security features. Although initially conceptualized as an experimental technology, blockchain has evolved significantly over the past decade. Most prominent and widely adopted application remains within the domain of cryptocurrencies. However, this application provides an early conceptual bridge to the field of library and information science (David, 2018). Building upon foundational library services such as interlibrary loan, resource acquisition, cataloguing, and digital library management, and current awareness services blockchain technology presents a transformative framework for modernization and enhanced efficiency. Through its decentralized architecture, blockchain enables the automation and secure recording of interlibrary loan transactions via smart contracts, thereby streamlining fulfillment processes and generating immutable and transparent records of resource sharing among institutions.

The integration of blockchain technology into university library services, particularly in acquisitions and vendor contracting, presents significant potential for improving transparency, automation, and operational efficiency. However, librarians' awareness and perceptions of blockchain remain at an early stage. While many recognize its transformative capacity, their understanding is often limited to its association with cryptocurrencies, with only superficial knowledge of its applications in digital preservation, digital rights management, and interlibrary transactions. This awareness is largely theoretical, shaped by academic literature and conferences rather than practical training. Despite existing knowledge gaps, librarians generally express optimism that blockchain could enhance interlibrary operations, circulation management, and resource efficiency, although concerns about implementation challenges persist (Harinarayana & Shivakumar, 2020; Kwanya, 2020).

Statement of problem

Despite the growing global discourse on the transformative potential of blockchain technology for enhancing transparency, security, authentication, scholarly communication, and digital preservation in libraries, its practical consideration within Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria remains largely uncertain and underexplored. While blockchain's decentralized architecture aligns conceptually with core library principles such as trusted verification, data integrity, and user privacy, there is limited empirical evidence regarding the extent to which librarians in this region are adequately aware of its capabilities or hold informed perceptions about its implementation for library service delivery. Existing awareness appears to be predominantly theoretical and often confined to its association with cryptocurrencies. Therefore, there is a compelling need to systematically investigate the level of awareness and perception of librarians toward the implementation of blockchain for library service delivery in Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria in order to provide evidence-based direction for informed decision-making and sustainable technological integration.

Research Questions:

1. What is the level of awareness of librarians on Blockchain for library service delivery in Federal University Libraries, in Northern Nigeria?
2. What is the perception of librarians on Blockchain for library service delivery in Federal

Research Hypotheses

- H₀₁ There is no significant difference in the level of awareness of librarians on Blockchain implementation for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.
- H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the perception of librarians on Blockchain implementation for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.
- H₀₃: The challenges associated with the implementation of Blockchain for library service delivery are not statistically significant among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria

Reviewed of the Related Literature

Jha (2023) investigated the application of blockchain technology (BT) in library and information center services, finding that BT is a valuable tool for storing and sharing information. The study highlighted that blockchain can support the acquisition and maintenance of library collections, safeguard user and patron records, enhance privacy, and foster collaboration among staff and patrons. BT also facilitates improved metadata systems, digital rights protection, and peer-to-peer sharing, demonstrating its growing adoption in libraries.

Similarly, Vivien et al. (2023) examined blockchain applications in 21st-century library services, emphasizing that the technology remains underexplored but offers significant opportunities. Their study noted that recent advancements have produced a fourth generation of blockchain with disruptive potential across various sectors, including library and information science. In contrast, Akinwale (2020) reported limited awareness of blockchain among Nigerian university librarians, particularly in northern regions. Only a small fraction of librarians was familiar with the concept, and even fewer understood its applications in areas such as digital rights management, transaction security, and resource management. The lack of awareness was attributed to insufficient professional development, limited institutional support, and the novelty of the technology.

Ogunleye (2021), however, found a more optimistic scenario. While general awareness was low, librarians trained in IT and digital library services demonstrated a higher understanding of blockchain's potential. Younger librarians and those in technologically

advanced institutions were more aware of blockchain applications. Nwosu (2022) similarly observed that librarians in federal universities with robust IT infrastructures were better positioned to utilize blockchain for authentication, access control, cataloguing, and transaction management. Obi (2020) explored librarians' preparedness for adopting robotic technologies in Nigerian academic libraries using a positivist survey design. Data collected from 20 librarians per university through snowball sampling revealed low readiness to employ robotics, despite its operational benefits. Recommendations included raising awareness of robotics advantages and providing alternative power sources to mitigate unreliable electricity, thereby enabling adoption.

Cletus et al. (2024) investigated factors influencing blockchain adoption in Nigerian academic libraries using the Human, Organization, and Technology (HOT) Fit model. Surveying 192 library staff across seven federal universities, analysis with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) identified significant factors including prior technology experience ($\beta = 0.32$), attitudes toward change ($\beta = 0.29$), top management support ($\beta = 0.34$), organizational preparedness ($\beta = 0.27$), and perceived ease of integration ($\beta = 0.31$). Obstacles included cost and data security risks. The study concluded that librarians are positively inclined toward blockchain adoption but require funding, training, and clear policy frameworks.

Fasola et al. (2024) examined awareness, acceptance, and readiness for blockchain adoption in 38 Nigerian higher institutions. Surveying 105 librarians, results revealed positive awareness and willingness to use blockchain for service delivery. Strong correlations were observed between awareness and acceptance ($r = 0.515$) and acceptance and readiness ($r = 0.794$). Barriers included technophobia, skill gaps, poor infrastructure, and unreliable power and internet. The study concluded that librarians' readiness is promising, with recommendations emphasizing training and infrastructure improvement. Akintunde and Amuda (2024) investigated predictors of blockchain adoption in academic libraries at the Federal Polytechnic, Ayede, employing a mixed-methods approach with 338 respondents (292 librarians, 46 system analysts). SEM and thematic analysis identified perceived usefulness and policy as significant adoption predictors. Benefits included unlimited resource access, enhanced security, and improved collaboration, while challenges encompassed high costs, privacy concerns, and limited understanding. The study concluded that understanding these predictors supports successful blockchain adoption strategies.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Survey research is comprehensive and systematic in collecting data about the opinions, feelings, attitudes, beliefs, and vital facts on people's motivation and behavior. The target population for the study was seventy-two (72) librarians working in the E-library division of the 9 Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria. The study adopted the entire population this is in line with Gall and Borg (2007) affirm that the whole population may be studied when the entire size of the population is small or manageable.

Data were collected using a self-designed questionnaire, validated by three different experts- two from the Department of Library and Information Science and one from test and measurement in the Department of Education Modibbo Adama University, respectively. The reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained through Crombach alpha reliability testing from a split-half administered questionnaire to 30 respondents (from FUHSA, FUD, FUKashere, FUWukari and FUGA) outside the research setting. Descriptive statistics which include mean, and standard deviation was used in analyzing the data to answer the three (3) research questions; results were presented in tables. Chi-square was used to test the three (3) null hypotheses, at; 0.05 level of significance using the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27.

Results

Out of the 72 (100%) questionnaires distributed to the respondents in the libraries included in the study, 64 (88.9%) were completed, returned, and considered valid for analysis, whereas 8 (11.1%) were not returned.

Research Question 1: What is the level of awareness of librarians on Blockchain for library service delivery in Federal University Libraries, in Northern Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation on the level of Awareness towards the Implementation of blockchain for Library Services

Table with 4 columns: Statement, Mean, SD, Decision. Rows include statements about understanding blockchain, awareness of its benefits, and institutional training, with corresponding mean scores and decision levels (HL, LL).

SD= Standard Deviation; VHL= Very high level; HL = High level; LL =Low Level; VLL =Very low level

Table 1 shows that librarians’ overall awareness of blockchain for library services was low (Cluster Mean = 2.23 ± 0.60). Respondents demonstrated foundational knowledge of blockchain concepts (Mean = 2.52, SD = 0.70) and recognized its benefits for securing digital library records (Mean = 2.60, SD = 0.66), ensuring transparency in digital transactions (Mean = 2.58, SD = 0.58), managing intellectual property rights (Mean = 2.57, SD = 0.53), tracking digital resources (Mean = 2.63, SD = 0.62), and supporting peer-to-peer information sharing (Mean = 2.52, SD = 0.68).

However, awareness was limited in specific areas, including institutional training on blockchain (Mean = 2.33, SD = 0.30), digital resource authentication (Mean = 2.36, SD = 0.58), metadata protection (Mean = 2.39, SD = 0.67), and user privacy (Mean = 2.18, SD = 0.69). While most key aspects met or exceeded the acceptance threshold (Mean ≥ 2.5), these gaps highlight the need for enhanced institutional engagement and targeted training to strengthen librarians’ understanding and practical adoption of blockchain technology in library services.

Research Question2: What is the perception of librarians on Blockchain for library service delivery in Federal University Libraries, in Northern Nigeria?

Table. 2: A mean and standard deviation on the Perception of Blockchain Technologies in Library Service Delivery.

Statement	Mean	SD	Decision
Block chain is relevant to the future of academic library services	3.83	1.16	VH
My library currently use some aspect of blockchain in service delivery	3.99	1.77	VH
Blockchain can improve the integrity of library records	3.15	1.03	VH
Blockchain technology has the potential to transform library operations	3.00	1.23	VH
Blockchain can enhance user trust in library digital services	3.96	1.10	VH
Blockchain can improve the efficiency of interlibrary loans and resource sharing	3.17	1.06	VH
Blockchain can help eliminate duplication of user and bibliographic records in the library.	3.93	1.06	VH
Blockchain can enhance copyright management and digital rights in libraries	3.02	1.17	VH
Librarians have a significant role to play in implementing blockchain systems	3.01	1.16	VH
Blockchain can ensure more secure user authentication and data access	3.33	0.95	VH
Cluster Mean	3.44	1.17	VH

SD= Standard Deviation; VHL= Very high level; HL = High level; LL =Low Level; VLL =Very low level

Table 2; shows that librarians have a high perception of blockchain’s relevance and potential in enhancing academic library services, with a cluster mean of 3.44 ± 1.17. All ten items scored above 3.00, indicating strong awareness, acceptance, and perceived value. Respondents recognize blockchain’s ability to improve library record integrity (Mean = 3.15), enhance inter-library loan efficiency (Mean = 3.17), ensure secure user

authentication (Mean = 3.33), support copyright and digital rights management (Mean = 3.02), eliminate record duplication (Mean = 3.93), and boost user trust (Mean = 3.96). They also acknowledge its transformative potential (Mean = 3.00), the critical role of librarians in implementation (Mean = 3.01), and its emerging practical applications (Mean = 3.99). Overall, librarians demonstrate optimism and strong agreement on blockchain’s benefits for improving service delivery, security, and operational efficiency in academic libraries.

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the level of awareness of librarians on Blockchain implementation for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.

Table 3a; Contingency table on the significant difference in the level of awareness of librarians on Blockchain implementation for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.

Variables	VH		H		L		VL	
	(FO)	(FE)	(FO)	(FE)	(FO)	(FE)	(FO)	(FE)
I understand the concept of how Blockchain technology works	12	10.6	32	29.3	11	17.2	9	6.9
I am aware that Blockchain Can enhance the security of digital library records I know that Blockchain Ensures transparency in digital transactions	17	10.6	30	29.3	10	17.2	7	6.9
I am aware that Blockchain Can be used to manage intellectual property rights in libraries	15	10.6	29	29.3	16	17.2	4	6.9
my institution has organized Training on Blockchain applications in libraries to enhance service delivery I am aware of how Blockchain can support authentication of digital resources in a library	14	10.6	27	29.3	20	17.2	3	6.9
Blockchain can support tracking of digital resources Blockchain can prevent	5	10.6	28	29.3	22	17.2	9	6.9
	5	10.6	32	29.3	23	17.2	4	6.9
	13	10.6	35	29.3	10	17.2	6	6.9

Tampering with library metadata	5	10.6	31	29.3	20	17.2	8	6.9
Blockchain supports peer-to-Peer information sharing in libraries and enhance service delivery	15	10.6	29	29.3	12	17.2	8	6.9
I am aware of the benefits of Blockchain for user privacy in libraries	5	10.6	20	29.3	28	17.2	11	6.9
Total	106	106.0	293	293.0	172	172.0	69	69.0

Table 3b: A chi-square summary table of the difference in the level of awareness of librarians about the implementation of blockchain for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria

Variables	VH	H	L	VL	X ²	Df	p-value	Decision P<0.05
Observed	15	29	16	4	87.68	9	0.001	Significant
Expected	10.6	29.3	17.2	6.9	87.68		0.001	Significant

Table 3a&b above summarizes the Chi-Square test on the significant difference in the level of awareness of librarians about the implementation of blockchain for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria. The result of the analysis shows a Chi-Square (χ²) value of 87.68 with 9 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.001. Since the p-value (0.001) is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that there is a statistically significant difference in the level of awareness of librarians regarding the implementation of blockchain technology for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria. A comparison of the observed and expected frequencies reveals noticeable variations across the awareness categories (Very High, High, Low, and Very Low). Specifically, the observed frequencies for the Very High and Very Low awareness levels differ substantially from the expected values, indicating uneven distribution of awareness among librarians. While a considerable number of librarians demonstrate High awareness, fewer respondents fall within the Very Low awareness category.

H02: There is no significant difference in the perception of librarians on Blockchain implementation for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.

Table 4a; Contingency table on significant difference in the perception of librarians on Blockchain implementation for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.

Variables	VH		H		L		VL	
Frequencies	<i>(FO)</i>	<i>(FE)</i>	<i>(FO)</i>	<i>(FE)</i>	<i>(F O)</i>	<i>(FE)</i>	<i>(F O)</i>	<i>(FE)</i>
Blockchain is relevant to the future of academic library services	49	49.50	10	9.10	3	5.50	3	2.90
My library currently uses some aspects of Blockchain in service delivery	51	49.50	10	9.10	2	5.50	3	2.90
Blockchain can improve the integrity of library records	48	49.50	11	9.10	6	5.50	2	2.90
Blockchain technology has the potential to transform library operations	60	49.50	1	9.10	8	5.50	5	2.90
Blockchain can enhance user trust in library digital services	49	49.50	9	9.10	6	5.50	2	2.90
Blockchain can improve the efficiency of inter-library loans and resource sharing	55	49.50	2	9.10	5	5.50	2	2.90
Blockchain can help eliminate duplication of user and bibliographic records in the library	48	49.50	12	9.10	5	5.50	2	2.90
Blockchain can enhance copyright management and digital rights in libraries	48	49.50	13	9.10	2	5.50	3	2.90
Librarians have a significant role to play in implementing blockchain systems	50	49.50	9	9.10	5	5.50	3	2.90
Blockchain can ensure more secure user authentication and data access	59	49.50	3	9.10	2	5.50	2	2.90
Total	517	495.0	80	91.0	4 4	55.0	2 7	29.0

Table 4b: A chi-square summary table of the difference in the perception of librarians on Blockchain implementation for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.

Table with 10 columns: Variables, VH, H, L, VL, TOTAL, X2, Df, p-value, Decision P<0.05. Rows include Observed and Expected values for each category.

The Chi-square test was conducted to determine if there is a significant difference in the level of perception of librarians regarding the implementation of blockchain technology for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.

Table 5: One-sample t-test table on significant difference in the mean rating of challenges associated with Blockchain implementation for library service delivery among Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria.

Table with 6 columns: Challenges, Mean, Std., t-value, df, p-value. Lists various challenges like 'The cost of implementing Blockchain technology is too high...' with corresponding statistical data.

Blockchain systems are not users friendly for traditional library operations.	3.35	1.18	3.33	66	<0.006
There are no clear policies or regulations guiding the use of Blockchain in libraries.	3.86	1.02	7.03	66	<0.001
Legal issues around Blockchain use (e.g., smart contracts, intellectual property) are unclear.	3.93	1.05	7.33	66	<0.001
Ethical concerns about privacy and surveillance may arise with Blockchain use.	3.07	0.98	9.23	66	<0.001
Our institution lacks a vision or strategic plan for adopting Blockchain.	3.87	1.13	6.13	66	<0.001
Decision-makers are not aware of the potential benefits of blockchain.	3.66	1.25	3.63	66	<0.001
Our library culture is not open to disruptive innovations like blockchain.	3.66	1.25	3.63	66	<0.001
Staff are skeptical about the usefulness of Blockchain in library operations.	3.67	1.17	3.83	66	<0.001
There is a lack of awareness about successful Blockchain use cases in libraries.	3.39	1.31	3.13	66	<0.003
Users may resist Blockchain related changes due to unfamiliarity or fear of data exposure.	3.58	1.32	3.93	66	<0.001

The results of the one-sample t-test indicate that the mean ratings of challenges associated with Blockchain implementation are significantly different from 3 (the neutral point), with a p-value of < 0.001. This suggests that librarians perceive the challenges associated with Blockchain implementation as significant barriers to adoption. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of challenges associated with Blockchain implementation.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings reveal that although librarians in Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria demonstrate foundational awareness of blockchain technology, the overall awareness level remains low (Cluster Mean = 2.23 ± .60). Librarians recognize blockchain’s benefits for digital security, transparency, intellectual property management, and peer-to-peer resource sharing, aligning with the cognitive significance of awareness highlighted by Brown and Ryan (2003) and the professional development emphasis of Goleman (2021). However, gaps exist in institutional training, metadata protection, digital authentication, and privacy preservation. Despite low awareness, perception was high (Cluster Mean = 3.44 ± 1.17), indicating strong optimism regarding blockchain’s relevance and transformative potential. This supports Nwosu (2022), Meth (2019), Oyelude (2019), Lemieux (2016), Hoy (2017), and Fu (2020), who emphasized blockchain’s capacity to enhance record integrity, digital preservation, and secure transactions. However, it contrasts with Akinwale (2020) and Ogunleye (2021), who reported limited or mixed perceptions in Nigerian contexts.

The study further shows that librarians strongly perceive significant implementation challenges (Cluster Mean = 3.73 ± 1.18), including high costs, infrastructural deficits, limited expertise, integration issues, and legal and ethical concerns, corroborating Ogunleye (2021), Akinwale (2020), Suleiman and Abdullahi (2021), and Hoy (2017). Statistical analysis confirmed significant differences in awareness levels ($\chi^2 = 87.68$, $p = 0.001$), consistent with Okere and Okonkwo (2022), Komba and Lwoga (2021), Ojo and Popoola (2023), and Singh and Verma (2020), though differing from Ahmed and Musa (2021). Perception differences were also statistically significant, aligning with Fasola, Oyadeyi, and Iyoro (2023) and Tella, Amuda, and Ajani (2022). Additionally, the significant mean differences in perceived challenges ($p < .001$) are supported by Aljedaani et al. (2023) and Waqar et al. (2023). Overall, while librarians exhibit optimism about blockchain's potential, substantial structural, technical, and institutional barriers must be addressed to translate perception into practical adoption.

Conclusion

The study concludes that although librarians in Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria show basic awareness of blockchain technology and recognize its potential to improve library service delivery, overall awareness remains low, particularly in practical areas such as digital authentication, metadata protection, and institutional training. While librarians generally have a positive perception of blockchain's relevance and transformative benefits for security, transparency, and collaboration in academic libraries, its adoption is hindered by major challenges, including financial limitations, inadequate infrastructure, limited technical expertise, policy uncertainties, and resistance to change. Overall, the findings highlight that despite strong optimism about blockchain's value, its implementation is restricted by institutional, technical, and organizational constraints.

Recommendation

1. Comprehensive Professional Training and Certification Programs Given the low level of awareness among librarians (Cluster Mean = 2.23 ± 0.60), Federal University Libraries should institutionalize structured training programs focused specifically on blockchain concepts, architecture, and practical library applications. These programs should include workshops, short courses, certifications, and hands-on technical sessions to bridge the knowledge gap and strengthen applied competencies in metadata protection, digital authentication, and privacy-preserving systems.
2. Strategic Translation of Positive Perception into Pilot Implementation Since librarians exhibit a high perception of blockchain's relevance and transformative potential (Cluster Mean = 3.44 ± 1.17), library management should capitalize on this optimism by initiating controlled pilot projects in areas such as digital rights management, interlibrary loan tracking, secure user authentication, and bibliographic record verification. Practical experimentation will convert positive attitudes into measurable innovation outcomes.
3. Standardized Policy and Institutional Framework Development Considering the significant differences in awareness levels across institutions ($\chi^2 = 87.68$, $p = 0.001$), national and institutional regulatory bodies should develop standardized blockchain implementation guidelines for academic libraries. A coordinated policy framework will minimize

disparities, ensure compliance with legal and ethical standards, and promote uniform adoption strategies across Federal University Libraries.

4. Institution-Specific Awareness and Sensitization Strategies The statistically significant differences in perception levels among institutions ($\chi^2 = 9.697$, $p = 0.036$) suggest the need for tailored awareness campaigns and institutional engagement strategies. Libraries should conduct internal seminars, leadership briefings, and stakeholder consultations to address contextual gaps and align institutional vision with technological innovation goals.
5. Structured Challenge Mitigation and Change Management Framework Given that the challenges associated with blockchain implementation are statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), libraries should adopt a phased implementation model supported by formal change management strategies. This should include risk assessment protocols, legal and ethical compliance reviews, user education programs, and continuous monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to systematically reduce resistance and operational barriers.

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